

Cover

Article: Do we need to innovate in critical care practice?

<p><i>When citing, sharing, or adapting this work, please provide proper attribution as follows:</i></p>	<p>Blanch, L., Maspons, R. & Palomar, G. <i>Do we need to innovate in critical care practice?. Crit Care. 2013 Jul 4;17(4):166. doi: 10.1186/cc12769.</i></p> <p>https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3706905/</p>
<p>ABSTRACT</p>	<p>Abstract not available</p>